

MRC

BIOMEDICAL DATA SCIENCE LEADERSHIP AWARDS

BETTER TEAMS, BETTER SCIENCE, BETTER HEALTH

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MRC BDSLA

The **MRC Biomedical Data Science Leadership Awards** (BDSLA) aim to strengthen the inclusion, quality, and recognition of data science within biomedical research by fostering thought leadership, innovative approaches, and a more inclusive research culture.

MRC BDSLA was launched in response to the **MRC's 2022 Biomedical Data Science Review**, which identified the need for coordinated action across four key challenges: developing strong biomedical data science leadership; improving access, recognition, and support for multidisciplinary teams; enhancing quality, standards, and professionalisation; and adopting inclusive approaches to growing skills capacity and improving career pathways.

In 2024, the MRC funded **five cross-institute collaborative awards** to address leadership and collaboration challenges and to generate evidence on how biomedical research can better incorporate, resource, and recognise high-quality data science across the research landscape. These projects bring together interdisciplinary teams to develop practical approaches, tools, and frameworks that can be adopted across the biomedical research community:

- **ABDC** – Advancing Biomedical Data Science Careers
- **BIOMEDASA** – Biomedical Data Science Accelerator

- **HxC** – Healthier Science through Collaboration
- **INTEGRATE** – Embedding a supportive culture for data science in biomedical research
- **PROMOTE** – Progressing Routes and Opportunities through Mentoring, Openness, Training, and Equity

Alongside their individual objectives for supporting interdisciplinary research, the five teams have developed strong **cross-award relationships**, supported by an innovative MRC mechanism that provided additional resources for collaborative activities. This multi-institute and cross-sector approach has enabled knowledge exchange across a wide range of UK research organisations regarding both barriers and new ways of working to support interdisciplinary research.

Our vision

Better Teams, Better Science, Better Health.

Driving an interdisciplinary biomedical data science culture that is visible, equitable, and impactful — giving funders, institutions, and researchers the evidence to drive real change in leadership, collaboration, recognition, and careers across UK biomedical research.

Our purpose

We exist to strengthen the foundations of data-driven biomedical research in the UK by addressing systemic barriers that constrain its societal impact. Drawing on robust, independent evidence, the Awards are delivering targeted resources and practical interventions across three interconnected challenges: structural barriers to interdisciplinary collaboration; limited and poorly defined pathways into leadership; and persistent lack of diversity within the data science workforce—notably, fewer than 25% of UK data professionals are women or from underrepresented groups, and only around 9% come from lower socio-economic backgrounds (DSIT, 2024).

By connecting researchers, industry and funders around shared priorities, the Awards are driving solutions-focused action to accelerate biomedical discovery—responsibly and equitably—in a landscape shaped by FAIR data principles and rapid advances in AI.

Cross-cutting themes

The five projects are working together to strengthen the evidence base across **five cross-cutting themes**, supporting the step change needed to embed high-quality data science in biomedical research. These themes focus on strengthening training and career pathways, advancing EDI, improving reward and recognition structures, fostering team science and positive research culture, and enabling cross-sector working and collaboration.

To achieve this, we have formed a cross-award collaboration that enables the sharing of knowledge and best practice, and the development of a shared evidence base and coordinated engagement activities.

1 Training and careers

Despite high demand, career pathways remain fragmented, with unclear progression, uneven access to mentorship, and inconsistent recognition of interdisciplinary work. We aim to strengthen career development and professional recognition for biomedical data scientists across sectors through structured mentoring programmes, skills development, and evidence generation to inform future workforce planning.

2 Equity, Diversity and Inclusion

Addressing workforce shortages without improving diversity risks limiting the perspectives that drive innovation. Across these awards, EDI is embedded as a core principle within programme design. We recognise that improving diversity in biomedical data science requires coordinated action across the education pipeline, workplace culture, and career progression. Sustainable change depends on embedding inclusion in leadership, governance, and everyday practice—not solely on recruitment.

3 Reward and recognition

Current reward and recognition frameworks often lag behind the evolving roles of biomedical data scientists, with inconsistent acknowledgment of methodological expertise, interdisciplinary contributions and technical career pathways. By generating evidence on how data science contributions are recognised in practice, we seek to inform policies and cultures that value diverse roles across sectors and better support progression, collaboration, and the development of high-quality, data-driven research.

4 Cross-sector working

Driving positive change in biomedical data science requires coordinated action across stakeholders and sectors. Collectively, the five projects are building and strengthening relationships with partners from across the ecosystem, from academia to industry, to maximise shared learning and improve the research culture and career pathways for biomedical data scientists across the UK.

5 Team science and research culture

Biomedical data science is inherently interdisciplinary, requiring diverse expertise and skillsets. Yet while research questions are increasingly integrative, institutional structures, funding mechanisms, and reward systems often remain discipline-bound. This misalignment can undermine collaboration, obscure contributions, and weaken research quality. We are engaging with the community to identify barriers to effective team science and what is needed to support successful collaboration.

Projects Overview

Our work across projects and shared themes

ABDC

Advancing Biomedical Data Science Careers

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ABDC is led by The Alan Turing Institute and EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), and **aims to document and professionalise skills, roles, and career pathways in biomedical data science while promoting effective team-science approaches.**

Key objectives

- Evaluate skills gaps across the ecosystem.
- Document roles, career pathways and team science approaches within the biomedical data science community.
- Recommend innovative ways of working that improve the visibility and inclusivity of data-driven research roles.

What we're doing

1 4

Map the landscape by identifying key stakeholders across the ecosystem and comparing selected competency frameworks to highlight skills gaps.

1 3

Establish minimal standards for creating and maintaining FAIR competency frameworks.

1 3

Assess training requirements based on landscape mapping (across its two components: stakeholders and competency frameworks)

3 2 5

Document individual, team and organisational experiences through interviews to inform evaluations and recommendations.

4

Identify challenges and opportunities for data sharing and collaboration agreements in biomedical AI research and development.

BIOMEDASA

Biomedical Data Science Accelerator

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The BIOMEDASA project is led by the University of Liverpool and aims to **strengthen interdisciplinary working in biomedical data science in a cost-effective, scalable way, while addressing workforce shortages and improving representation in the field.**

Key objectives

- Build a sustainable, equitable, diverse, and nationally scalable Biomedical Data Science workforce.
- Embed Data Science as a core capability in Biomedical and Clinical research, elevating standards of practice.
- Adopt a systems approach to enable evidence-led investment and coordination across the training landscape.

What we're doing

- 3 4 5 Establish scalable models for embedding data expertise in resource-constrained health research environments.
- 1 4 5 Deliver scalable, accessible training to standardise open science practices, improve data quality & FAIR, and accelerate responsible adoption of generative AI.
- 1 2 4 Identify training gaps and sector needs through evidence-based analysis of student and postgraduate provision.
- 1 2 5 Develop structured, career-transition pathways into data science through targeted mentoring programmes.
- 1 2 4 Creating reusable outreach frameworks that raise awareness of data science careers to young people, expanding and diversifying the talent pipeline.

HxC

Healthier Science through Collaboration

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The HxC project is led by the University of Edinburgh, HDR UK, and the UK Dementia Research Institute, and aims to **amplify the voices of interdisciplinary scientists from diverse backgrounds while fostering sustainable culture change by embedding good practices within research teams and organisations.**

Key objectives

- Draw on insights from diverse stakeholders to challenge longstanding issues in interdisciplinary research culture.
- Develop evidence-based tools and training, and integrate good research culture practices to maximise the future impact of UK biomedical data research.

What we're doing

- 1 2 4 Establish Early Career Researcher, Oversight, and Patient, Public and Industry Involvement groups to shape project outputs.
- 2 5 Survey researchers' experiences of interdisciplinary work to understand challenges and good practices.
- 2 3 5 Co-design a Code of Conduct Toolkit for interdisciplinary teams to develop bespoke guidelines fostering equitable, respectful and effective collaboration.
- 1 2 5 Develop a CPD-accredited training programme for interdisciplinary teams, hosted on HDR UK's Futures Learning Platform.
- 2 3 5 Evaluate the impact of these tools through real-world application and reflection with interdisciplinary teams.

INTEGRATE

INTEGRATE

Embedding a supportive culture for data science in biomedical research

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INTEGRATE is led in collaboration with the University of Oxford, HDR UK, CRUK Data Community Support Unit and University of Dundee aiming to **identify, pilot and evaluate initiatives that strengthen data science career pathways and drive better collaboration across UK biomedical science.**

Key objectives

- Strengthen interdisciplinary career development and routes for progression.
- Enable effective collaborative working and team science.
- Facilitate mobility between disciplines and sectors.

What we're doing

- 1 3 5 Map existing good practice in UK academic data science career support through survey and interviews.
- 1 5 Pilot a national interdisciplinary peer-mentoring programme to connect researchers across biomedicine and data science.
- 1 2 4 Feasibility studies into mobility opportunities including cross-sector and interdisciplinary secondments, shadowing and consultancy.
- 1 5 Evaluation of initiatives for building interdisciplinary and collaborative skills and networks (e.g. hackathons and career development workshops).
- 3 5 Explore the use and barriers to adoption of Code of Conducts to facilitate effective team research.

PROMOTE

PROMOTE

Progressing routes and opportunities through mentoring, openness, training and equity

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The PROMOTE project is led by the University of Leeds in collaboration with the Universities of York, Sheffield, Teesside, and Newcastle, and aims to **understand career pathways and barriers for mid-career biomedical data scientists in academia, industry and the NHS, while supporting their progression into leadership roles and easing cross-sector career transitions.**

Key objectives

- Uncover barriers to leadership progression in organisational culture and structures.
- Embed EDI principles in everything we do.
- Discover and develop best practice on how to overcome career progression barriers.

What we're doing

- 1 5 Map career pathways in academia, industry and the NHS using a co-created survey and semi-structured interviews.
- 3 Analyse university HR promotion policies across the UK and assess their suitability for biomedical data scientists.
- 1 4 Pilot a national mid-career to senior-career mentoring programme to support the development of leadership skills and career confidence.
- 1 4 Facilitating interdisciplinary communication and knowledge sharing through a Hackathon event.

Collaborative work

The MRC Biomedical Data Science Leadership Awards have been intentionally configured as a **coordinated, cross-award ecosystem** with collaboration embedded as a core design principle.

Each award tests complementary interventions within its local context, but with a clear expectation that outputs are transferable, comparable, and contribute to a common evidence base. This creates a federated model in which learning is accumulated across sites, enabling a more robust understanding of what works, for whom, and under which conditions.

This collaboration goes beyond passive alignment, it actively **amplifies impact, creating opportunities to achieve more together than would be possible in isolation** and accelerating reach and adoption across the UK ecosystem.

We do this through regular meetings that bring together project managers and leads to strengthen collaboration, coordinated communications, and events that engage wider stakeholders and embed evidence-based good practice across the research sector.

We have also established **cross-award Working Groups** focused on common project themes to enhance knowledge sharing and collaboration. Current groups include Stakeholder Engagement, EDI, and Mentoring.

In parallel, we are working with a consultant to ensure our work leaves a **lasting legacy**, while our cross-award approach is shaping new ways of funding and evaluating impact, **shifting the focus from isolated project metrics to contributions within a connected national system**.

By demonstrating how initiatives can be mutually reinforcing, well-resourced, and inclusive of diverse stakeholders, the programme is laying the foundation for future national investments, not only in biomedical data science but also in interdisciplinary work designed to be collaborative, strategically aligned, and scalable.

Delivery teams

ABDC

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BIOMEDASA

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Cancer Research UK Data Science Community
Francis Crick Institute
International Society for Computational Biology (iSCB)
Karolinska Institutet
Northern Health Science Alliance
Clinical AI Interest Group at The Alan Turing Institute
University of Glasgow
University of Manchester

NHS

Alder Hey Children's Hospital
Barnsley Hospital NHS Foundation Trust
Liverpool University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust
Liverpool Women's Hospital
Manchester Royal Infirmary
Manchester University NHS Foundation Trust
NHS England
West Yorkshire Integrated Care Board

INDUSTRY / OTHER

Association of British HealthTech Industries
AstraZeneca
Digital Health Ethos
Eliptica
GlaxoSmithKline
IBM
IntoUniversity
IQVIA
Liverpool City Region Combined Authority
Medipex
North West Business Leadership Team
Pinpoint Data Science

Get in touch

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Contact form

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